

SELECTION OF THE OPTIMAL 6 KV POWER SUPPLY SCHEME

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The selection of the optimal 6 kV power supply scheme plays a crucial role in ensuring the reliability, efficiency, and economic feasibility of the power supply system. By choosing an optimal scheme, energy resources can be used efficiently, equipment lifespan can be extended, and system reliability can be enhanced. This approach prevents unnecessary energy losses and reduces the likelihood of equipment failures caused by incorrect scheme selection.

The importance of an optimal power supply scheme lies in its ability to minimize energy losses, thereby reducing production costs and improving energy efficiency. Additionally, a well-selected scheme ensures the reliability of the power supply system, prevents failures, reduces maintenance costs, and guarantees the stability of production processes.

When selecting the optimal power supply scheme, it is necessary to consider several critical factors. These include the nature of the loads and their fluctuations, the reliability of the power supply source, and the technical parameters of the equipment. By correctly evaluating and analyzing these factors, the most efficient and reliable scheme can be selected. Conversely, an incorrectly chosen scheme reduces the operational efficiency of the system, increases the frequency of failures, and raises overall costs.

Optimal schemes simplify the management of essential parameters needed for the stable operation of the system, reducing power supply interruptions. As a result, production processes become more efficient and reliable.

The primary focus of this section is on the optimal method for connecting transformer substations (TPs) to the feeder. Basic schemes are generally divided into two types: trunk and radial (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Basic Power Supply Schemes: a) Radial, b) Trunk

Trunk Scheme: This type of scheme is organized by connecting multiple transformer substations (TPs) to a single trunk line. The trunk scheme is primarily used for covering long distances and allows energy transmission from a single primary power source to multiple networks. The main advantages of trunk schemes are as follows:

- High efficiency in power delivery.
- Improved supply safety and stability.
- High reliability, as even if there is an interruption in one part of the trunk line, power supply can continue through other parts.

Radial Scheme: In the radial scheme, each transformer substation (TP) is independently supplied from its source. This scheme is mainly used for small or medium-sized networks. The advantages of radial schemes include:

- Lower construction and operational costs.
- Simplicity and speed in maintenance.
- Independence of each element of the scheme, making it easier to detect and eliminate problems in the system.

In the 6 kV rural power supply, the selection of an optimal scheme involves examining all combinations of radial and trunk schemes.

The selection of an optimal power supply scheme is conducted through three methods:

1. Designing;
2. Modernization;
3. Evaluation of existing schemes.

These three methods differ based on the type of input data. The primary input data include the location and capacity of transformer substations (TPs). In

the design method, several potential points for TP installation are determined. In the modernization and evaluation of existing schemes methods, the current TP locations are already established, but in the modernization method, newly proposed TP locations can also be introduced.

In conclusion, the methods of designing, modernization, and evaluation of existing schemes are selected based on available data. Correctly assessing the necessary parameters through these methods is essential for choosing the optimal scheme and ensuring the stable operation of the system. As a result, selecting the optimal scheme contributes to providing a power supply system with high efficiency and reliability.

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